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Role of Mathematics Teachers at Secondary School Level of Education: Implication for National Development in Nigeria

Aliyu, Ganiyatu

Email: aliyuganiyatu@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 08035374735

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State

Abstract

Secondary education remains a solid bridge in terms of knowledge gain in Nigerian school systems. Secondary education serves as the epicenter of the knowledge acquired by learners from pre-primary, primary, and basic education up to the college, polytechnic, and university levels. This paper focuses on mathematics teachers' role in secondary school education and its implications for national development. Secondary school education remains at the epicenter of levels of education, being the kind of education received by learners after primary education before they proceed to tertiary institutions. It also highlighted the role of mathematics teachers in secondary education for sustainable national development. However, the study concluded that the need for effective teaching of mathematics at the secondary school level of education is very important for sustainable national development. Therefore, a quality secondary education system will produce vibrant human resources that can be beneficial to Nigeria in terms of a sustainable economy and technological development. The paper, among others, recommended that Implement comprehensive teacher preparation programs that emphasize both deep content knowledge and effective pedagogical approaches in mathematics education, provides ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education, pedagogy, and technology integration and ensure that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated for their expertise and dedication, fostering a sense of value and appreciation for their contributions and encourage mathematics teachers to pursue specialization and expertise in specific areas of mathematics, such as algebra, geometry, or statistics, to enhance their teaching proficiency.

Keywords: Mathematics, teachers' role, secondary education, national development.

Introduction

In view of the fast-growing technologically and scientifically engineered society of today, mathematics is a very important subject in that regard. Mathematics is a highly structured and important subject, and its teaching and learning deserve the highest level of seriousness from teachers in order to meet the desired national goal. Mathematics is a compulsory subject taught in both primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. Mathematics and its applications are all-encompassing, which explains its renown as an "everyday" subject and its importance in the curriculum. Today, it is a reality that it is the creation, mastery, and utilization of modern science and technology that basically differentiate the developing from the developed nations of the world. (Okeke, 2016) The foundation of science and technology, which is the basic requirement for the development of a nation, is mathematics (Eunice, 2020).

The National Policy on Education recommends the teaching of mathematics at all levels of education. In a similar vein, the National Policy on Science and Technology envisages an education system that shall emphasize all levels and re-orient the entire society towards scientific thinking in order to develop new technologies and adapt existing ones to improve societal wellbeing and security. The government has demonstrated commitment to this end by, among other things, directing that university admission into the science and liberal arts disciplines be in the ratio of 60 to 40 percent, respectively, and has even gone further to establish universities of science and technology (Eunice, 2020). Therefore, mathematics plays a vital role in nation-building, and mathematics is crucial for many careers and job opportunities in today's increasingly technological society. This study intends to clarify the concepts of mathematics teachers, secondary education, and national development with the intent of presenting the reciprocal benefits of one to the other.

Mathematics education is the practice of teaching and learning mathematics, as well as the scholarly research that goes with it in modern education (NCTM, 2000). Mathematicians are interested in the tools, methods, and approaches that make practice easier. The industrial revolution resulted in a massive increase in urban populations in the 18th and 19th centuries. Basic numeric skills, such as telling time, counting money, and simple arithmetic, were essential in this new urban lifestyle.

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Mathematics is integrated into the curriculum from an early age in the new public education systems. By the twentieth century, mathematics was taught in all developed countries as part of the core curriculum. The cultural impact of the "electric age" was also taken up by educational theory and the teaching of mathematics in the twentieth century, whereas previous approaches focused on "working with specialized problems in arithmetic" (Clements & Guryan, 2015). They also postulated that the "electric age" transformed mathematics education in the 20th century. The authors argue that the "electric age" led to a shift in the focus of mathematics education from "working with specialized problems in arithmetic" to a more conceptual and broad-based approach. They also discuss the role of technology in mathematics education, both in the 20th century and today. Here are some specific examples of how the "electric age" influenced mathematics education:

1. The invention of the calculator led to a shift away from rote memorization of arithmetic facts and towards a more conceptual understanding of mathematics.
2. The development of computers led to the creation of new tools for teaching and learning mathematics, such as computer algebra systems and dynamic geometry software.
3. The internet has made it possible for students to access a wealth of mathematical resources, including online textbooks, tutorials, and simulations.

The "electric age" has had a profound impact on mathematics education, and its influence is likely to continue in the years to come. Small children were meditating on number theory and sets as part of the emergent structural approach to knowledge (Clements & Guryan, 2015). The methods used in any given context are heavily influenced by the goals that the relevant educational system is attempting to achieve.

In order to have a viable system of education that can pilot the stirring of national development in Nigeria and any other country in the world, teachers play most of the important roles needed, which can be instilled in the learners through imitating teachers (Agan, 2010). Teachers, not only of mathematics but of every subject, perform most of the critical roles in setting the future goals that every nation intends to achieve for growth and development (Sarick, 2020). This is because teachers are the second parents to every school-going age, from elementary schools through senior secondary levels (pre-primary, primary, and secondary schools). Teachers go to great lengths to ensure that students achieve the highest level of learning and are responsible in their future endeavors. Throughout their service periods, teachers consider what is best for the students and where they should be placed around the world. Teachers' good intentions are only to help and invest heavily in national growth and development.

Mathematics Teacher at Secondary School level of Education

A mathematics teacher is someone who inspires students to look beyond the pages of the textbook to become problem solvers and critical thinkers. As a mathematics teacher, you are ensuring that your students will have the knowledge and skills that will help them not only succeed in the classroom but also be empowered by mathematics to become productive citizens of our democratic society. (NCTM, 2019) According to Odogwu and Odafe (2013), a mathematics teacher is a purposeful leader who impacts mathematics information or skills on another individual or group of individuals. Therefore, a mathematics teacher is one who organizes the mathematics learning experience in a conducive environment where learning can conveniently take place. Mathematics teachers are also individuals who assist others in acquiring mathematical knowledge. Singh (2010) outlined, among other things, the following qualities of a good mathematics teacher for effective mathematics teaching in secondary school settings: 1) He must possess a basic qualification in the subject 2) In terms of abilities, he must be aware of his students' capabilities 3) He must be an innovator who changes teaching strategies, techniques, texts, and material and 4) He must be a model of enthusiasm for not only mathematics but other subjects in the curriculum. From the above, mathematics teachers are the sole agents in the teaching and designing of learning. The bedrock of the development of any nation could be traced to education, while education cannot exist without teachers.

Mathematics at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Education is a tool that avails people of knowledge, skill, technique, and information, which empowers them to know their rights and duties toward the family, society, and nation. One of the most important benefits of education in a society is that it improves the standard of living and allows individuals to contribute to the development of the nation or society (Adam, 2016). Secondary education is the basic catalyst that will bring about the development of an individual and society. The importance of secondary education in our educational system cannot be overemphasized. Apart from serving as a link between primary and secondary education, it provides the opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge, skills, and traits beyond the primary level. A major factor that necessitates the acquisition of secondary education in Nigeria is that the education

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being provided at the primary level is proving insufficient for a child to acquire the permanent literacy, communication, and numeracy skills expected of him or her at the end of the training. Ige, (2011). Also, secondary education remains at the centre, being the kind of education received by learners after primary education before they proceed to tertiary institutions (FRN, 2013). The following are the aims and objectives of secondary education in Nigeria as stipulated in the national policies on education: 1) preparation of students for useful living within society 2) preparation of students for higher education 3) Diversification of the curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities, and roles opened to students after their secondary school course; 4) Raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, and 5) Fostering Nigerian unity with an emphasis on communities that unite us in our diversity. According to the above terms and objectives, secondary school is the bridge between the primary and tertiary levels. It is the springboard from which all the students of higher education take off, and all primary school leavers must pass through it to become useful to them, their families, and society. According to Lere (2014), who pointed out that Nigeria is a country in search of development and that national development is realizable through general education.

Mathematics for sustainable National Development

National development is the ability of a country to improve the social welfare of its people. It involves the development of infrastructure such as roads, hospitals, airports, schools, quality education, and the health sector, as well as the development of its citizens. According to Easterly (2021), economic development is an essential component of national development, but it is not the only factor. True national development requires a broader set of conditions that promote inclusive growth, equitable distribution of resources, and sustainable progress. Easterly's work provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex relationship between economic development and national development. Ichipi and Panya (2016) proposed that national economic development can be defined as a country's or nation's overall development or collective socioeconomic, political, and religious advancement. Also, national development can be viewed as the capacity of the country to raise the standard of living of its residents. It can be accomplished by providing individuals with the necessities of life, such as food and shelter, as well as employment.

Significant role of Mathematics Teachers for sustainable National Development

Gadanidis and Petoczky (2022) are of the view that mathematics teachers play an indispensable role in shaping the future of nations. By nurturing critical thinking, fostering innovation, promoting informed decision-making, preparing students for the future of work, and cultivating global citizenship, mathematics teachers are not merely educators; they are architects of sustainable national development. Investing in mathematics teachers is an investment in the future of humanity, paving the way for a world that is more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable. A mathematics teacher should realize that the mathematics classroom is an artificial environment full of individuals with their own learning experiences. The role of secondary mathematics teachers in promoting national development is critical in the country. Most of the Key Roles of Mathematics Teachers in Sustainable National Development as provided by Gadanidis and Petoczky, (2022, p. 419) are highlighted as;

1. Nurturing Critical Thinkers and Problem-Solvers: Mathematics teachers equip students with the ability to analyse information, evaluate arguments, and formulate creative solutions to challenges, fostering a citizenry capable of addressing societal issues effectively.
2. Promoting Innovation and Creativity: Mathematics teachers encourage students to think outside the box, embrace experimentation, and explore new ideas, fostering a culture of innovation that drives progress and advancement.
3. Empowering Informed Decision-Making: Mathematics literacy is crucial for informed decision-making, enabling individuals to make sound choices about their own lives and contribute to the development of their communities.
4. Preparing for the Future of Work: Mathematics education equips students with the skills and adaptability necessary to thrive in an ever-changing employment landscape, characterized by automation, technological advancements, and new industries.
5. Fostering Global Citizenship: Mathematics provides a common language that transcends cultural and linguistic barriers, enabling individuals to collaborate and address global challenges effectively.

Also, the provides that Investing in Mathematics Teachers can help in recognizing the transformative power of mathematics education, governments and educational institutions must prioritize investments in mathematics teachers. This includes:

1. High-Quality Teacher Training: Providing aspiring mathematics teachers with rigorous training programs that emphasize both content knowledge and pedagogical skills.

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2. Continuous Professional Development: Offering ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education and pedagogy.
3. Competitive Compensation and Support: Ensuring that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated and provided with the resources and support they need to be effective in their roles.
4. Promoting Collaboration and Mentorship: Fostering a culture of collaboration and mentorship among mathematics teachers, enabling them to share best practices and support each other's professional growth.
5. Recognizing Excellence: Acknowledging and celebrating the achievements of outstanding mathematics teachers, inspiring others and raising the overall quality of mathematics education.

In a comprehensive manner, the contribution of secondary education to national development cannot be overemphasized. Secondary schools serve as the recruitment grounds for the tertiary institutions in the country. Secondary education supplies the needed manpower for national development. According to Kasim & Usman (2019), a developed or educated society is one that has enough manpower and each person occupies his or her rightful position to enhance the growth of the society. Secondary education promotes social and group relationships. The school system within the educational system fosters this development. The school brings people of different cultural backgrounds together for a common purpose. Secondary education also promotes the culture of productivity by enabling individuals to discover their creative potential and apply it. The improvement of their existing skills and techniques when performing specific tasks, thereby increasing the efficiency of their personal and societal efforts.

Mathematics teachers and educators have an important role to play in national development. A mathematics teacher should realize that the mathematics classroom is an artificial environment full of individuals with their own learning experiences. It is well known that the quality and extent of learner achievement are determined primarily by teacher competence, sensitivity, and motivation. The National Council for Teacher Education has defined teacher education as "a program of education, research, and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education levels." Teacher education is a program related to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein. The role of secondary mathematics teachers in promoting national development is critical for a country like Nigeria. Mathematics teacher education has to become more sensitive to the emerging demands of the school system. For this, it has to prepare mathematics teachers for a dual role as stated by Arora, (2002, p.24) in a book titled "mathematics teachers and their teaching" as to;

1. encouraging, supportive, and humane facilitator in teaching-learning situations who enables learners (students) to discover their talents, realize their physical and intellectual potentialities to the fullest, develop character and desirable social and human values to function as responsible citizens, and,
2. An active member of the group of persons who make conscious effort to contribute towards the process of renewal of the school curriculum to maintain its relevance to the changing societal needs and personal needs of learners, keeping in view the experiences gained in the past and the concerns and imperatives that have emerged in the light of changing national development goals and educational priorities

The role of mathematics teachers in Nigeria and many other developing countries cannot be overemphasized. Even with the advent of technology, no tool has been able to completely replace a teacher. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) maintained that no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Mathematics teachers have an important role to play in promoting national development. When all students are educated in a classroom environment, mathematics teachers are capable of handling and guiding all the students in the classroom in teaching and learning, which can help to promote national development. Therefore, teachers of mathematics, with their developed skills, can impart mathematical knowledge to students in a classroom environment in order to help them become self-reliant and productive individuals since mathematics is the bedrock of all civilizations. Mathematics knowledge gained from a mathematics teacher assists students in making future plans. The knowledge of mathematics is being applied everywhere, like in the economy of a country and the construction of buildings, among others. With the knowledge of mathematics, students can practice agriculture, and mathematics plays a role in investments, advertising, revenue generation, and investment.

If we go by the position acclaimed by mathematics as true, then paying lip service to it would not make its benefits a reality. A new attitude must be adopted on the part of the government to reward the teaching and learning of mathematics. Not only the government but all stakeholders' students, teachers, parents, and the entire society should be committed to mathematics teaching and learning. The government's first and most beautiful step has been to make mathematics a core subject in the school curriculum from primary to secondary school levels. The mathematics teacher is the sole stakeholder in the national development that this study is based on, especially secondary school mathematics teachers. The teacher is pivotal in the

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acquisition of mathematical knowledge (Afolabi, 2020). Adler and Rippin (2023) discuss the role of the teacher as a mentor in mathematics education. They argue that effective mathematics teachers go beyond simply imparting knowledge and skills; they act as mentors, guiding and supporting students as they develop their mathematical understanding. Based on the Adler and Rippin (2023) report several key characteristics of effective mathematics mentors are identified as:

1. Deep understanding of mathematics: Mentors should have a deep understanding of the mathematics they are teaching, enabling them to provide clear explanations, answer students' questions effectively, and identify and address misconceptions.
2. Ability to connect mathematics to real-world contexts: Mentors should be able to connect mathematical concepts to real-world applications, making mathematics more relevant and engaging for students.
3. Strong communication and interpersonal skills: Mentors should have strong communication and interpersonal skills, enabling them to create a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable asking questions and taking risks.
4. Ability to differentiate instruction: Mentors should be able to differentiate instruction to meet the needs of all learners, providing appropriate challenges and support for students at different levels of mathematical proficiency.
5. Passion for mathematics: Mentors should have a passion for mathematics, which is contagious and can inspire students to develop their own love of the subject.

Adler and Rippin (2023) conclude that mentoring is essential for effective mathematics education. They argue that by acting as mentors, teachers can help students develop the confidence, perseverance, and problem-solving skills they need to succeed in mathematics and beyond.

Conclusion

Mathematics as a subject is vital to understanding many other subjects. A good understanding and knowledge of mathematics is an indispensable instrument in many other fields, including the social sciences, engineering, medicine, and the natural sciences. Based on the importance of mathematics, it is hereby concluded that without mathematics, there can be no development. Investing in mathematics teachers is an investment in Nigeria's future. By enhancing their training, fostering a culture of collaboration, addressing resource deficiencies, promoting innovative teaching strategies, and supporting their well-being, Nigeria can empower its mathematics teachers to play a pivotal role in shaping the nation's development. Through effective mathematics education, Nigeria can nurture a generation of critical thinkers, problem-solvers, and innovators capable of driving sustainable progress and prosperity.

Recommendations

To produce good mathematics education output at the secondary school level in Nigeria therefore, this study recommends among others that there is need for stakeholders, government, school administrators and non-governmental organisations to;

1. Implement comprehensive teacher preparation programs that emphasize both deep content knowledge and effective pedagogical approaches in mathematics education.
2. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education, pedagogy, and technology integration and ensure that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated for their expertise and dedication, fostering a sense of value and appreciation for their contributions
3. Encourage mathematics teachers to pursue specialization and expertise in specific areas of mathematics, such as algebra, geometry, or statistics, to enhance their teaching proficiency.
4. Establish collaborative learning communities among mathematics teachers to share best practices, discuss challenges, and provide mutual support and Encourage peer observation and feedback sessions among mathematics teachers to provide constructive feedback and improve teaching practices.
5. Provide mathematics teachers with access to up-to-date textbooks, supplementary resources, and technology tools for effective instruction and incorporate real-world applications of mathematics into lessons to demonstrate the relevance of mathematics to students' lives and future careers.
6. Upgrade and maintain mathematics laboratories with modern equipment, technology, and software to support hands-on learning and experimentation.

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7. Ensure that all secondary schools have reliable internet access to facilitate online learning resources, professional development opportunities, and communication with colleagues and Integrate technology effectively into mathematics instruction to enhance visualization, data analysis, and problem-solving capabilities
8. Encourage mathematics teachers to incorporate active learning strategies, such as project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and collaborative problem-solving, to engage students and promote deeper understanding

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